

S1 Appendix

This file provides supplementary Figs, tables, and methods for Oliphant NP, Sy Z, Ray N, *et al.*, Optimising scale-up and deployment of community health workers in Mali: a geospatial analysis. 2022.

Table of Contents

Supplementary Fig 1. Health system pyramid and health service delivery networks included in analysis	3
Supplementary Figs 2-5. Simplified analysis flow diagram	4
Supplementary Fig 6. Digital elevation model at 1 km x 1 km resolution	8
Supplementary Fig 7. Estimated population count per grid cell beyond 5 km from a CSRef or CSCoM in 2020 at 1 km x 1 km resolution	9
Supplementary Fig 8. Estimated count of U5 deaths per grid cell beyond 5 km from a CSRef or CSCoM in 2020 at 1 km x 1 km resolution	10
Supplementary Fig 9. Estimated <i>Pf</i> malaria cases among all ages (0-99 years) per grid cell beyond 5 km from a CSRef or CSCoM in 2020 at 1 km x 1 km resolution	11
Supplementary Fig 10. Road network	12
Supplementary Fig 11. Land cover at 1 km x 1 km resolution	13
Supplementary Fig 12. Merged land cover at 1 km x 1 km resolution	14
Supplementary Fig 13. CSRef + CSCoM network in 2020	15
Supplementary Fig 14. Workflow for deriving the potential ASC sites for the hypothetical ASC network	16
Data	16
Administrative boundaries.....	16
Health system pyramid and health service delivery networks	16
Existing ASC network.....	18
Candidate ASC sites for optimized ASC networks	18
DEM	18
Land cover	19
Roads	19
Rivers and other water bodies.....	19
Merged land cover	19
Travel scenario tables	19
Population.....	21
Estimated under-five deaths	21
Estimated <i>Plasmodium falciparum</i> malaria cases.....	21
Analysis	22
Assessing the efficiency of ASC deployment	22
References	34

Supplementary Fig 1. Health system pyramid and health service delivery networks included in analysis.

Source health facilities: MSDS, DHIS2. Source ASC: MSDS⁸

"CARTOGRAPHIE_ASC_MARS_2021_DGSHP_31.03.2021_VF2.xls". MSDS=Ministère de la santé et du développement social; CSRef=Centre de santé de référence; CSCoM=Centre de santé communautaire; ASC=Agent de santé communautaire.

A.

B.

Supplementary Fig 2. Simplified analysis flow diagram for preparation of population input layers

(A) Analysis flow for preparation of estimated population, estimated U5 deaths layers, and estimated *Pf* malaria cases layers in 2020. (B) Analysis flow for preparation of vector point shapefiles for potential ASC sites for hypothetical ASC networks

Supplementary Fig 3. Simplified analysis flow diagram for geographic coverage with the processing order prioritizing the estimated population within 30 minutes walking of an ASC

(A) Analysis flow for estimates and maps of geographic coverage of the estimated population >5 km of a CSCoM or CSRef in cells with >=150 people in 2020 by a hypothetical ASC network deployed to optimize geographic coverage of the estimated population at 1 km x 1 km resolution. (B) Analysis flow for estimates and maps of geographic coverage of the estimated U5 deaths >5 km of a CSCoM or CSRef in cells with >=150 people in 2020 by a hypothetical ASC network deployed to optimize geographic coverage of the estimated population at 1 km x 1 km resolution. (C) Analysis flow for estimates and maps of geographic coverage of the estimated *Pf* malaria cases >5 km of a CSCoM or CSRef in cells with >=150 people in 2020 by a hypothetical ASC network deployed to optimize geographic coverage of the estimated population at 1 km x 1 km resolution. Blue boxes represent data inputs. Orange boxes represent analysis steps. Grey boxes represent outputs. IHME = Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation. MAP = Malaria Atlas Project. U5 = children under-five years of age. *Pf* = *Plasmodium falciparum*.

Supplementary Fig 4. Simplified analysis flow diagram for geographic coverage with the processing order prioritizing the estimated U5 deaths within 30 minutes walking of an ASC

(A) Analysis flow for estimates and maps of geographic coverage of the estimated population >5 km of a CCom or CSRef in cells with >=150 people in 2020 by a hypothetical ASC network deployed to optimize geographic coverage of the estimated U5 deaths at 1 km x 1 km resolution. (B) Analysis flow for estimates and maps of geographic coverage of the estimated U5 deaths >5 km of a CCom or CSRef in cells with >=150 people in 2020 by a hypothetical ASC network deployed to optimize geographic coverage of the estimated U5 deaths at 1 km x 1 km resolution. (C) Analysis flow for estimates and maps of geographic coverage of the estimated *Pf* malaria cases >5 km of a CCom or CSRef in cells with >=150 people in 2020 by a hypothetical ASC network deployed to optimize geographic coverage of the estimated U5 deaths at 1 km x 1 km resolution. Blue boxes represent data inputs. Orange boxes represent analysis steps. Grey boxes represent outputs. IHME = Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation. MAP = Malaria Atlas Project. U5 = children under-five years of age. *Pf* = *Plasmodium falciparum*.

Supplementary Fig 5. Simplified analysis flow diagram for geographic coverage with the processing order prioritizing the estimated *Pf* malaria cases within 30 minutes walking of an ASC

(A) Analysis flow for estimates and maps of geographic coverage of the estimated population >5 km of a CSCCom or CSRef in cells with >=150 people in 2020 by a hypothetical ASC network deployed to optimize geographic coverage of the estimated *Pf* malaria cases at 1 km x 1 km resolution. (B) Analysis flow for estimates and maps of geographic coverage of the estimated U5 deaths >5 km of a CSCCom or CSRef in cells with >=150 people in 2020 by a hypothetical ASC network deployed to optimize geographic coverage of the estimated *Pf* malaria cases at 1 km x 1 km resolution. (C) Analysis flow for estimates and maps of geographic coverage of the estimated *Pf* malaria cases >5 km of a CSCCom or CSRef in cells with >=150 people in 2020 by a hypothetical ASC network deployed to optimize geographic coverage of the estimated *Pf* malaria cases at 1 km x 1 km resolution. Blue boxes represent data inputs. Orange boxes represent analysis steps. Grey boxes represent outputs. IHME = Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation. MAP = Malaria Atlas Project. U5 = children under-five years of age. *Pf* = *Plasmodium falciparum*.

Supplementary Fig 6. Digital elevation model at 1 km x 1 km resolution.

NASA SRTMGL1 version 003 (approximately 30 m x 30 m), resampled to 1 km x 1 km and 100 m x 100 m (later not shown). Accessed 15 January 2021.¹

Supplementary Fig 7. Estimated population count per grid cell beyond 5 km from a CSRef or CCom in 2020 at 1 km x 1 km resolution.

Population layers produced at 1 km x 1 km resolution and 100 m x 100 m resolution (latter not shown) resampled from Worldpop² census disaggregated gridded population estimates (constrained) at approximately 90 m x 90 m resolution for Mali in 2020, version 2.0², corrected to official population counts from the Institut National de la Statistique du Mali (INSTAT),¹⁰ and clipped to the area beyond 5 km from the CCom and CSRef networks.

Supplementary Fig 8. Estimated count of U5 deaths in 2020 per grid cell beyond 5 km from a CSRef or CCom in 2020 at 1 km x 1 km resolution.

Estimated count of U5 deaths in 2020 at 1 km x 1 km derived from the mean U5 mortality rate in 2015 (IHME³) at 5 km x 5 km, resampled to 1 km x 1 km and multiplied by the infant population in 2020 (derived from Worldpop,^{21,22,2} see pages 22-23 below for methods) at 1 km x 1 km and clipped to the area beyond 5 km from the CCom and CSRef networks.

Supplementary Fig 9. Estimated *Pf* malaria cases among all ages (0-99 years) per grid cell beyond 5 km from a CSRef or CCom in 2020 at 1 km x 1 km resolution.

Annual mean incidence of *Plasmodium falciparum* (*Pf*) malaria among all ages (0-99 years) in 2020 globally at 2.5 arcminutes (approximately 5 km x 5 km) resolution from Weiss et al 2019⁴, reprojected to 1 km x 1 km resolution, multiplied by the estimated population in 2020², and clipped to the area beyond 5 km from the CCom and CSRef networks.

Supplementary Fig 10. Road network

HOTOSM Mali Roads (OpenStreetMapExport)⁵

Supplementary Fig 11. Land cover at 1 km x 1 km resolution.

Land cover at 1 km x 1 km resolutions. Discreet land cover classes are based on the UN Land Cover Classification System (LCCS)⁶

Supplementary Fig 12. Merged land cover at 1 km x 1 km resolution.

Merged land cover at 1 km x 1 km and 100 m x 100 m resolutions (latter not shown) derived using the Merge land cover tool in Accessmod 5.6.56⁷

Supplementary Fig 13. CSRef + CSCom network in 2020.

Source: HeRAMS Mali⁹

Supplementary Fig 14. Workflow for deriving the potential ASC sites for the hypothetical ASC network.

A. Estimated population count per grid cell in 2020 at 1 km x 1 km resolution resampled from Worldpop² census disaggregated gridded population estimates (constrained) at approximately 90 m x 90 m resolution for Mali in 2020, version 2.0², corrected to official population counts from the Institut National de la Statistique du Mali (INSTAT).¹⁰ B. Area beyond 5 km from a CSRef or CSCCom in 2020 derived from latitude and longitude of health facilities from HeRAMS Mali.⁹ C. Estimated population count per grid cell beyond 5 km from a CSRef or CSCCom in 2020 at 1 km x 1 km resolution. D. Grid cells with at least a population of 250 beyond 5 km from a CSRef or CSCCom in 2020 at 1 km x 1 km resolution. E. Potential sites for the hypothetical ASC network covering the estimated population in grid cells with at least 250 population beyond 5 km from a CSRef or CSCCom in 2020 at 1km x 1km resolution.

Data

Administrative boundaries

We obtained vector official shapefiles for administrative boundaries (national, regional, commune) from the Institut Géographique du Mali (IGM).¹⁰⁻¹² We reprojected the shapefiles for the administrative boundaries from the Coordinate Reference System (CRS) EPSG:4326, WGS 84 to the CRS EPSG:32629 - WGS 84 / UTM zone 29N using the GDAL “Warp” tool in QGIS 3.14.¹⁴ See Public Data Repository at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6551988>

Health system pyramid and health service delivery networks

During the year of focus of the study, 2020, the Ministry of Health and Social Development (French acronym MSDS) provided overall leadership, coordination and governance for the health system composed of public, private, community and confessional institutions. The central level MSDS supervised regional health management teams. Regional health management teams supervised district health management teams. District health management teams supervised health facilities. Per the national health management information system (DHIS2), as of 2020, the health system included 3135 health facilities divided into four levels: a tertiary referral level, a secondary referral level, a primary referral level, and primary level.¹⁵ The tertiary referral level included five national public sector specialty and teaching hospitals in the national capital, Bamako, providing specialty care, referral/counter-referral services from/to the secondary referral level, and emergency services. The secondary referral level was composed of eight

regional public sector hospitals located in regional capitals providing secondary referral/counter-referral services from/to the primary referral level, and emergency services. The primary referral level was composed of 68 district public sector hospitals (*Centre de santé de référence*, CSRef in French). The primary level was composed of 3054 health facilities, including 1521 public sector community health centres (*Centre de santé communautaire*, CSCCom in French) and 1533 private sector health facilities providing a minimum package of primary health care services and referral/counter-referral services to/from primary referral facilities (see Supplementary Fig 13). CSCCom were designed to serve the population within 5 km.¹⁵ CSCCom were managed by a Technical Director (Directeur Technique du Centre or DTC in French) and community health associations and collectives (known by the French acronym ASACO).¹⁵

At the base of the primary level were paid, full-time CHWs, known as agents de santé communautaire (ASC in French) providing community-based primary health care services, including prevention, promotion, and curative services, conducting surveillance activities, and supervising part-time community health volunteers known as *relais*.¹⁶ The focus of our analysis was on the ASC. The *relais* were beyond the scope of the current analysis.

The following summarizes points from the national community health strategy of 2016-2020¹⁶ relevant to our analysis:

- Definition of ASC: ASC were a standardized type of paid, full-time CHW, recruited from and living in the community they serve, and recognized by the MSDS as meeting standard, minimum criteria for ASC.
- Package of services: ASC were allowed to provide a minimum package of services standardized and defined by the MSDS and implemented in the context of the national community health strategy (*Soins essentiels dans la communauté*). The minimum package included a focus on basic primary health care services, including prevention, promotion, and curative services. This included household visits to promote reproductive, maternal, newborn and child health and nutrition interventions, water and sanitation interventions, provide family planning, provide integrated community case management of diarrhoea, pneumonia, and malaria, screening for acute malnutrition among children under-five, monitoring of vital events such as births and deaths, disease surveillance; participation in mass campaigns (e.g. for childhood vaccinations, distribution of seasonal malaria chemoprevention, and long-lasting insecticide treated bednets) and supervision of the *relais* (community health volunteers).
- Deployment: ASC were deployed to ASC sites: villages selected by the ASACO where the ASC lived and worked and, in principle, located in rural areas beyond 5 km from a CSCCom. The catchment of an ASC was defined as the area within 3-4 km of the ASC site. For our analysis, and in agreement with the MSDS, we defined the catchment of the ASC as the area within 30 minutes walking of the centroid of the 1 km x 1 km grid cell containing an ASC site. ASC sites were, in principle, the largest village within the catchment area of the ASC which also included satellite villages (i.e., villages apart from the ASC site but within the ASC catchment area and meant to be served by the ASC through outreach).
- ASC to population ratio: The national community health strategy 2016-2020 indicated a norm of 1 ASC per 700 population in the regions of the Center and South (Kayes, Koulikoro, Mopti, Segou, and Sikasso) and 1 ASC per 300-500 population in the regions of the North (Gao, Tombouctou, Kidal, Menaka, and Taodénit). For our analysis, and in agreement with the MSDS, we used the ratio of 1 ASC per 700 population for the regions of the Center and South and 1 ASC per 500 for the regions of the North. For our analysis, Bamako was not considered eligible for ASC per MSDS norms the population was within 5 km of a CSCCom. Note that the non-governmental organization MUSO supported ASC in Yirimadio, an impoverished neighbourhood within Bamako.
- Supervision: ASCs were attached to the nearest CSCCom for supervision and resupply.

Because the national DHIS2 did not contain geographic coordinates for all CSRef and CSCCom, we obtained global positioning system (GPS) coordinates for CSRef and CSCCom in 2020 from HeRAMS Mali,⁹ including for 66/68 CSRef in the DHIS2 (97%; the remaining two CSRef were being planned/were under-construction) and 1513/1521 CSCCom in the DHIS2 (99%) in the form of a vector point shapefile dataset in the CRS EPSG:4326, WGS 84 (see Supplementary Figs 13 and 14). We reprojected the vector point shapefile to the CRS EPSG:4326, WGS 84 to the CRS EPSG:32629 - WGS 84 / UTM zone 29N using the GDAL “Warp” tool in QGIS 3.14.¹⁴

Existing ASC network

We obtained a Microsoft Excel file containing the count of existing, functional ASC (n=3104) by supervising CSCCom, district and region as of March 2021 from the MSDS based on the ASC master list compiled by the MSDS in March 2021.⁸

Candidate ASC sites for optimized ASC networks

For our hypothetical scale-up scenarios and analysis of the efficiency of ASC deployment we prepared a dummy raster file at 1 km resolution representing all candidate ASC sites for the optimized ASC networks (see Supplementary Figs 1 for the analysis flow).

We used the following steps:

1. We conducted a buffer analysis to produce a vector shapefile of the area beyond 5 km from a CSCCom or CSRef and rasterized the vector shapefile at 1 km resolution using the “Rasterize” function in QGIS 3.14.¹⁴
2. We used the “Clip raster” function in QGIS 3.14¹⁴ to clip the raster layer for the estimated population at 1 km x 1 km by the vector shapefile from step 1 above to produce a raster layer for the estimated population beyond 5 km from a CSCCom or CSRef at 1 km x 1 km resolution.
3. To identify candidate cells for the optimized ASC networks, we created a raster at 1 km x 1 km resolution containing cells where the estimated population in 2020 beyond 5 km of a CSCCom or CSRef (from step 2 above) was at least 150 people using the “Raster calculator” function in QGIS 3.14.¹⁴
4. We created a vector point layer from the raster in step 3 above using the “Raster pixels to points” function in QGIS 3.14.¹⁴ The resulting vector point layer contained point features at the centroid of every cell at 1 km x 1 km resolution where the estimated population in 2020 in areas beyond 5 km from a CSCCom or CSRef was at least 150 people, resulting in 12050 candidate sites for the optimized ASC networks beyond 5 km from a CSCCom or CSRef.
5. We added the following variables to the vector point layer:
 - a. A variable called “Ratio” that reflected the region-specific ratio of ASC per population per MSDS norms (1 ASC per 700 population in the regions of the South and Center and 1 ASC per 500 population in regions of the North).
 - b. A variable called “PopAire” that was an extract of the population within 30 minutes walking of the hypothetical ASC site based on a geographic coverage analysis of the population beyond 5 km from a CSRef or CSCCom by the hypothetical ASC network (n=12050 hypothetical ASC sites) without considering a maximum population capacity (i.e., capacity set to 10000000) using the walking in dry conditions travel scenario. (See Analysis section, Methods for Targeting research question 1)
 - c. A variable called “Numb_ASC” equal to the “PopAire” / “Ratio” rounded up to the nearest whole number, giving a total number of 15843 hypothetical ASC in 12050 hypothetical ASC sites.
 - d. A variable called CAP reflecting the maximum population capacity of each hypothetical ASC site based on the number of hypothetical ASC in the hypothetical ASC site (from variable c) multiplied by the variable “Ratio”.

All hypothetical ASC networks had the same number of hypothetical ASC sites (n=12050) and number of hypothetical ASC (n=15843) as a starting point with the only difference being the order or deployment (i.e., processing order). See the section below on the analysis of the efficiency of ASC deployment for further details on how the number of CHWs per candidate site within the hypothetical networks was calculated and how the final sites among the candidate sites were selected for each optimized network.

DEM

We obtained a Tagged Information File Format (GeoTiff) raster of a digital elevation model (DEM) – the NASA Shuttle Radar Topography Mission Global 1 arc second (SRTMGL1) dataset version 3.0, with a resolution of approximately 30 meters (m) x 30 m (0.000277778 decimal degrees) for the area including Mali.¹ The SRTMGL1 was retrieved 7 February 2021 from the online EarthExplorer, courtesy of the NASA EOSDIS Land Processes Distributed Active Archive Center (LP DAAC), USGS/Earth Resources Observation and Science (EROS) Center,

Sioux Falls, South Dakota, <https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov/>. More information on the SRTMGL1 is available at <https://lpdaac.usgs.gov/node/527>. We prepared a DEM raster at 1 km x 1 km resolution using the GDAL “warp” tool in QGIS 3.14¹⁴ to reproject the CRS of the original file from EPSG:4326, WGS 84 to the CRS EPSG:32629 - WGS 84 / UTM zone 29N, resample the resolution to 1 km x 1 km using bilinear as the resampling method and clip the file to the extent of the administrative level 0 (adm0) shapefile. See GeoTIFF file “Dem_SRTM_finale_1Km.tif” in Public Data Repository at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6551988>.

Land cover

We obtained a GeoTIFF raster for land cover in Africa [c_gls_LC100-LCCS_201501010000_AFRI_PROBAV_1.0.1.tif] at a resolution of approximately 100m x 100m from the Copernicus Global Land Service,⁶ accessed on 27 March 2018 at <https://land.copernicus.eu/global/products/lc>. The land cover dataset contains discreet land cover classes based on the UN Land Cover Classification System (LCCS). Further details on the Copernicus land cover data set are available at <https://land.copernicus.eu/global/products/lc>. We prepared a GeoTIFF land cover raster (see the GeoTIFF file “Landcover_Copernicus_finale_1Km.tif” in Public Data Repository <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6551988>) using the GDAL “warp” tool in QGIS 3.14¹⁴ to reproject the CRS from EPSG:4326 - WGS84 to CRS EPSG:32629 - WGS 84 / UTM zone 29N, resample the resolution to 1 km x 1 km using nearest neighbour as the sampling method and clip the file to the extent of the final DEM.

Roads

We obtained a vector line shapefile on 12 January 2022 for the road network in Mali from the IGM.⁵ To prepare the final roads file, we added a variable called “label” for the road type that reclassified the road types in variable “Viabilite” using the standard OpenStreetMap categories described at <https://wiki.openstreetmap.org/wiki/Key:highway>; added a “class” variable in order to enable linking with the travel time scenarios; and reprojected the CRS from EPSG:4326 - WGS84 to CRS EPSG:32629 - WGS 84 / UTM zone 29N in alignment with the final DEM using the GDAL “warp” function in QGIS 3.14.¹⁴ See file [Routes_du_pays_32629.shp] in Public Data Repository at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6551988>. As described below in the section on the merged land cover raster, we uploaded the vector line shapefile for the road network into our Accessmod 5.6.56⁷ project at 1 km x 1 km resolution and used the merge land cover tool in Accessmod 5.6.56⁷ to rasterize the vector line shapefile for the road network as part of the merged land cover raster at 1 km x 1 km resolution.

Rivers and Other Waterbodies

“Permanent water bodies”, “temporary water bodies”, and “herbaceous wetland” land classes within the land cover layer (above) were considered barriers to movement, where they were not crossed by a road. See above for information on the land cover layer.

Merged land cover

For our geographic accessibility analysis, we prepared a merged land cover raster at 1 km x 1 km resolution using the “Merge land cover” tool in Accessmod 5.6.56.⁷ See file [raster_land_cover_merged_Landcover_merge_1km.tif] in Public Data Repository at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6551988>. The process is described in detail in Ray et al, 2008.⁷ In brief, the “Merge land cover” tool stacks, orders, and merges the road network, barriers (rivers and other waterbodies, the later from the land cover), and land cover files into a single raster dataset.

Travel scenario tables

We developed a travel scenario table for walking in dry conditions. See file [Supplementary Table_t_scenario_walk_dry.xls] in Public Data Repository at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6551988>. We set traveling speeds for each land cover class and road class. Travel speeds were adapted from previous studies in the region.^{7,17,18} Travel speeds refer to the population going to the ASC.

Population

Data preparation of the raster layer for the estimated population beyond 5 km from a CSRef or CSCoM in 2020

We obtained a GeoTiff raster for the estimated population count for Mali in 2020 at roughly 100m x 100m resolution [mli_ppp_2020_UNadj_constrained.tif] from <https://www.worldpop.org/geodata/summary?id=49699>, courtesy of Worldpop, accessed 17 December 2021.² The 2020 population count layer was developed following the Random Forest (RF)¹⁹-based dasymetric mapping approach²⁰ and building footprints²¹ and adjusted to match the corresponding United Nations Population Division (UNPD). Details are provided at the link above. We also obtained official population estimates at commune level for 2020 from the Institut National de la Statistique du Mali (INSTAT).¹⁰

1. We reprojected the original 2020 Worldpop GeoTiff raster file for the population count in 2020 at approximately 100 m resolution from the CRS EPSG:4326 - WGS84 to the CRS EPSG:32629 - WGS 84 / UTM zone 29N in alignment with the final DEM using the GDAL “warp” function in QGIS 3.14¹⁴ and aggregated the reprojected raster to 1 km resolution using the r.resamp.stats GRASS 7.8.2 plugin in QGIS 3.14¹⁴ with sum as the aggregation method and the final DEM at 1 km resolution as the extent.
2. We clipped the raster from step 1 to the area beyond 5 km from a CSCoM or CSRef using the buffer analysis and clip raster tools in QGIS 3.14.¹⁴
3. We used a spatial join to copy the official population estimates at commune level for 2020 from INSTAT to the vector file for communes in CRS EPSG:32629 - WGS 84 / UTM zone 29N [Lim_Com_Pop_2019_2020_05_11_2020_V2.shp].¹³
4. We used the “Zonal statistics” tool in QGIS 3.14¹⁴ to calculate the count of the population from the raster of the 2020 population beyond 5 km from a CSCoM or CSRef at 1 km x 1 km from step 1 to the commune vector file [Lim_Com_Pop_2019_2020_05_11_2020_V2.shp].
5. We created a ratio in the commune vector file [Lim_Com_Pop_2019_2020_05_11_2020_V2.shp] that divided the official population estimates at commune level in 2020 from INSTAT from step 3 by the estimated population count beyond 5 km from a CSCoM or CSRef at commune level for 2020 from step 2.
6. We rasterized this ratio at 1 km resolution using the “Rasterize” tool in QGIS 3.14¹⁴ with the ratio from step 4 as the burn and the extent of the DEM at 1 km resolution as the extent. Using raster calculator in QGIS 3.14¹⁴ we multiplied the rasterized ratio by the Worldpop population in 2020 at 1 km x 1 km resolution to create a GeoTiff raster for the population in the year 2020 unadjusted for the population on barriers (rivers and other water bodies).
7. We uploaded the file raster from step 5 into Accessmod 5.6.56⁷ and redistributed the population on cells with barriers to cells without barriers within the same commune, resulting in the final raster file for the population in the year 2020 [Pop_residual_from_corrected_layer.tif].

See Public Data Repository at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6551988>.

Data preparation of the raster layer for estimated live births beyond 5 km from CSRef or CSCoM in 2020

We obtained a GeoTiff raster [MLI_births_pp_v2_2015.tif] for the estimated live birth count in 2015 for Mali, adjusted to UNPD estimates at roughly 1 km x 1 km resolution in Geographic Coordinate system WGS84 from Worldpop, accessed on 17 December 2021.²² We also obtained a GeoTiff raster [mli_ppp_2015_1km_Aggregated_UNadj.tif] for the estimated count of the population in 2015 for Mali, adjusted to UNPD estimates at roughly 1 km x 1 km resolution in Geographic Coordinate system WGS84 from Worldpop, accessed on 17 December 2021.²³ We prepared a GeoTiff raster layer for the estimated count of live births in the area beyond 5 km from a CSCoM or CSRef in 2020 at 1 km x 1 km resolution to be used in our targeting analysis for under-five deaths using the following steps:

1. We reprojected the rasters for the estimated live births in 2015 and estimated population in 2015 to CRS EPSG:32629 - WGS 84 / UTM zone 29N in alignment with the final DEM using the GDAL “warp” function in QGIS 3.14.¹⁴
2. We used the raster calculator tool in QGIS 3.14¹⁴ to create a new raster for the ratio of the estimated live births in 2015 to the estimated population in 2015.

3. We used the raster calculator tool in QGIS 3.14¹⁴ to create a new raster for estimated live births in 2020 constrained to the footprint of the raster for the estimated population in 2020 by multiplying the raster for the ratio from step 2 above by the raster for the estimated population in 2020.²
4. We created a raster for the estimated live births in the area beyond 5 km from a CSCoM or CSRef in 2020 [MLI_birth_2020_beyond_5km.tif] by clipping the raster for the estimated live births in 2020 to the area beyond 5 km of a CSCoM or CSRef, using the clip raster tool QGIS 3.14.¹⁴ See Public Data Repository at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6551988>.

Data preparation of the raster layer for the estimated under-five deaths beyond 5 km from a CSRef or CSCoM in 2020

We used the following steps to prepare the raster layer for the estimated count of under-five (0-5 years old) deaths in Mali in the area beyond 5 km from a CSCoM or CSRef in 2020 at 1 km x 1 km resolution to be used in our targeting analysis:

1. We obtained a GeoTiff raster file [IHME_LMICS_U5M_2000_2017_Q_UNDER5_MEAN_Y2019M10D16.tif] for modelled pixel-level estimates of the mean probability of under-five (0-5 years old) mortality (also known as the under-five mortality rate or U5MR) in EPSG:4326 - WGS84 at 2.5 arcminutes (approximately 5 km x 5 km) resolution developed by the Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation (IHME),³ accessed on 12 January 2022, at <http://ghdx.healthdata.org/lbd-data>.
2. We used Raster Calculator in QGIS 3.14¹⁴ to create a new raster equivalent to band 18 (U5MR for 2017) of the raster from step 1 in EPSG:4326 - WGS84 at approximately 5 km x 5 km resolution, maintaining the extent of the raster from step 1.
3. Using the GDAL Warp tool in QGIS 3.14,¹⁴ we reprojected the raster for the U5MR in 2017 from step 1 above to CRS EPSG:32629 - WGS 84 / UTM zone 29N at 1 km x 1 km resolution, with nearest neighbour as the resampling method and the extent aligned to the raster for the total population in 2020.
4. We used Raster Calculator in QGIS 3.14¹⁴ to multiply the raster for the U5MR in 2017 from step 2 above by the raster for estimated live births in 2020, resulting in a raster for the number of U5 deaths in 2020 [Number_of_death_U5] assuming the U5MR in 2020 was equivalent to the U5MR in 2017, in CRS EPSG:32629 - WGS 84 / UTM zone 29N at 1 km x 1 km resolution.
5. We created a raster for the estimated U5 deaths in 2020 in the area beyond 5 km from a CSCoM or CSRef [Number_of_residual_death_U5.tif] by clipping the raster of the estimated U5 deaths in 2020 from step 4 above to the area beyond 5 km from a CSCoM or CSRef using the clip raster tool in QGIS 3.14.¹⁴ See Public Data Repository at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6551988>.

Note that we did not need to adjust for the estimated under-five deaths on barriers because this step was conducted when preparing the raster for the estimated live births in 2020.

Data preparation of the raster layer for the estimated *Plasmodium Falciparum* malaria cases among all ages (0-99 years) beyond 5 km from a CSRef or CSCoM in 2020

We used the following steps to prepare a GeoTiff raster layer for the estimated count of *Plasmodium falciparum* (Pf) malaria cases among all ages (0-99 years) in Mali in 2020 at 5 km x 5 km resolution to be used in our targeting analysis:

1. We obtained a GeoTiff raster file for modelled pixel-level estimates of the annual mean incidence of (Pf) malaria among all ages (0-99 years) in 2019 globally at 2.5 arcminutes (approximately 5 km x 5 km) resolution [2020_GBD2019_Global_Pf_Incidence_Rate_2019.tif] developed by the Malaria Atlas Project,⁴ accessed on 12 January 2022, at <https://malariaatlas.org/malaria-burden-data-download/>.
2. Using the GDAL Warp tool in QGIS 3.14¹⁴, we reprojected the raster for mean incidence of Pf malaria (all ages) in 2019 to CRS EPSG:32629 - WGS 84 / UTM zone 29N at 1 km x 1 km resolution, using the extent of the raster for the estimated total population in 2020 as the extent.

3. We used the “Raster calculator” tool in QGIS 3.14¹⁴ to prepare a GeoTiff raster for the count of *Pf* malaria cases among all ages (0-99 years) in 2020 at 1 km x 1 km resolution [Number_Malaria_cases_final.tif] by multiplying the reprojected raster for the mean incidence of *Pf* malaria (all ages) in 2019 from step 2 [2020_GBD2019_Global_Pf_Incidence_Rate_2019.tif] by the raster for the estimated total population in Mali in 2020 with the CRS EPSG:32629 - WGS 84 / UTM zone 29N at 1 km x 1 km resolution, using the extent of the raster of the estimated population in 2020 as the extent.
4. We used the “Raster calculator” tool in QGIS 3.14¹⁴ to prepare a GeoTiff raster for the estimated count of *Pf* malaria cases in 2020 in areas beyond 5 km from a CSRef or CSCoM [Number_Malaria_cases_residual_final.tif] by multiplying the estimated count of *Pf* malaria cases in 2020 from step 3 above by a dummy raster for the area beyond 5 km from a CSRef or CSCoM (see Public Data Repository at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6551988>).

Note that we did not need to adjust for the estimated *Pf* malaria cases on barriers because this step was conducted when preparing the raster for the estimated population in 2020.

Analysis

Assessing the efficiency of ASC deployment

We assessed the efficiency of deployment of hypothetical scaled-up ASC networks in terms of geographic coverage of a) the estimated population in areas beyond 5 km of a CSRef or CSCoM in 2020 b) the estimated under-five deaths in areas beyond 5 km of a CSRef or CSCoM in 2020 and c) the estimated *Pf* malaria cases in areas beyond 5 km of a CSRef or CSCoM in 2020. We identified the best performing hypothetical scale-up scenario in terms of efficiency of deployment across outcomes.

Hypothetical ASC networks in areas beyond 5 km from a CSRef or CSCoM:

- a. Hypothetical ASC network deployed to prioritize the estimated population in areas beyond 5 km from a CSRef or CSCoM in 2020 by ordering the processing order (deployment) based on the estimated population in areas beyond 5 km from a CSRef or CSCoM in 2020 within the catchment area of a given ASC, prioritizing catchments with a higher estimated population over those with a lower estimated population.
- b. Hypothetical ASC network deployed to prioritize the estimated under-five deaths in areas beyond 5 km from a CSRef or CSCoM in 2020 by ordering the processing order (deployment) based on the estimated under-five deaths in areas beyond 5 km from a CSRef or CSCoM in 2020 within the catchment area of a given ASC, prioritizing catchments with a higher estimated number of under-five deaths over those with a lower estimated number of under-five deaths.
- c. Hypothetical ASC network deployed to prioritize the estimated *Pf* malaria cases among all ages (0-99 years) in areas beyond 5 km from a CSRef or CSCoM in 2020 by ordering the processing order (deployment) based on the estimated number of *Pf* malaria cases in areas beyond 5 km from a CSRef or CSCoM in 2020 within the catchment area of a given ASC, prioritizing catchments with a higher estimated number of *Pf* malaria cases over those with a lower estimated number of *Pf* malaria cases.

We defined geographic coverage as the theoretical catchment area of a health service delivery location, within a maximum travel time, accounting for the mode of transportation and the maximum population capacity of the type of health service delivery location.⁷ We used the "geographic coverage" module of AccessMod 5.6.56⁷ for all analyses. The maximum travel time was set at 30 minutes walking in dry conditions for ASCs, with direction of travel from the ASC to the population. The number of ASCs per candidate ASC site was based on the MSDS norm for the ASC to population ratio (1 ASC per 700 population in regions of the Center and South and 1 ASC per 500 population in the regions of the North)¹⁵ applied to the estimated population beyond 5 km from a CSRef or CSCoM and within 30 minutes walking in dry conditions of the ASC site. The maximum population capacity for ASCs was per the MSDS norms for the ratio of ASCs per population by region (1 ASC per 700 population in regions of the Center and South and 1 ASC per 500 population in the regions of the North).¹⁵ The maximum extent of a catchment was therefore delimited by the maximum travel time of 30 minutes walking in dry conditions except in cases where

the estimated population in the catchment exceeded the maximum population capacity of the ASC – in which case the extent of the catchment was smaller than the maximum travel time and was defined by the area containing the estimated population, up to the maximum population capacity.

Special note for geographic coverage of estimated under-five deaths and *Pf* malaria cases: Because there is no normative limit on the number of under-five deaths or *Pf* malaria cases that can be covered by an ASC, for geographic coverage of the estimated number of under-five deaths and *Pf* malaria cases we did not use a maximum population capacity and therefore the extent of a catchment was delimited by the maximum travel time of 30 minutes walking in dry conditions.

Research questions

1. What was the geographic coverage of the estimated population beyond 5 km from a CSRef or CSCoM in 2020 for each hypothetical ASC network? Which hypothetical ASC network was most efficiently deployed in terms of geographic coverage of the estimated population beyond 5 km from a CSRef or CSCoM in 2020?
2. What was the geographic coverage of the estimated under-five deaths beyond 5 km from a CSRef or CSCoM in 2020 for each hypothetical ASC network? Which hypothetical ASC network was most efficiently deployed in terms of geographic coverage of the estimated under-five deaths beyond 5 km from a CSRef or CSCoM in 2020?
3. What was the geographic coverage of the estimated *Pf* malaria cases among all ages (0-99 years) beyond 5 km from a CSRef or CSCoM in 2020 for each hypothetical ASC network? Which hypothetical ASC network was most efficiently deployed in terms of geographic coverage of the estimated *Pf* malaria cases beyond 5 km from a CSRef or CSCoM in 2020?
4. Which hypothetical ASC network was the best performing in terms of efficiency of deployment across outcomes?

Step 1. “Dummy” geographic coverage analysis of the estimated population beyond 5 km of a CSCoM or CSRef using the hypothetical ASC network deployed to prioritize the estimated population.

Overview of the step

Answering research question 1 for the hypothetical ASC network deployed to prioritize the estimated population required two steps: a “dummy” geographic coverage analysis step, meaning a geographic coverage analysis that ignored the maximum population capacity of each ASC site and a “real” geographic coverage analysis step. The “dummy” geographic coverage analysis in Step 1 helped to derive the estimated population for each ASC site catchment area (the area within a 30-minute walk from the ASC in dry conditions), variable “PopAire”, which was used for the processing order in Step 2 (answers research question 1), Step 10 (answers research question 2) and Step 11 (answers research question 3) for the hypothetical ASC network deployed to prioritize the estimated *Pf* malaria cases.

The objective was to derive the estimated population for each ASC site catchment area (the area within a 30-minute walk from the ASC in dry conditions) which was needed to calculate the number ASC needed at each site and the processing order for the “real” geographic coverage analysis in Step 2 below. We used the excel output from Step 1 to calculate the number of ASC needed at each ASC site and to establish the processing order for the real geographic coverage analysis in Step 2. We calculated the number of ASC needed at each ASC site based on the MSDS norms noted above and the estimated population for each ASC site catchment area. For example, if the estimated population of the catchment area for ASC site #6523 was 13801 in a region of the North (where MSDS norm = 1 ASC per 700 population) the number of ASC needed would be 28 (rounded). We created a new variable called “CAP” for the maximum capacity of the ASC site based on the estimated number of ASC needed at each site. In the example above, “CAP” for ASC site #6523 would be 14000 (28 x 700). In Step 2 we conducted the real geographic coverage analysis using the estimated catchment population from step 1 (in descending order) as the processing order and “CAP” as the maximum population coverage. Details are provided below.

Data preparation

See Methods section “Candidate ASC sites for optimized ASC networks” for details on preparation of the hypothetical ASC network.

See Methods section “Data preparation of the raster layer for the estimated population beyond 5 km from a CSRef or CSCoM in 2020” for details on preparation of the raster layer for the estimated population beyond 5 km from a CSRef or CSCoM in 2020.

Analysis

We conducted a “dummy” geographic coverage analysis of the estimated population in areas beyond 5 km from the CSRef or CSCoM in 2020 by the hypothetical network of ASC (n=12050 ASC sites with 15843 ASC) deployed to prioritize the estimated population at 1 km x 1 km resolution for the walking in dry conditions travel scenario. We set the maximum travel time to 30 minutes. We set the maximum population capacity for ASCs as 10000000 to effectively ignore capacity. We used a descending processing order (highest to lowest) based on the estimated population beyond 5 km from a CSRef or CSCoM in 2020 within each 30-minute catchment area. This prioritized the deployment of the hypothetical ASC network according to the size (highest to lowest) of the estimated population in areas beyond 5 km from a CSRef or CSCoM within each 30-minute catchment.

- a. We used the following data inputs:
 - i. Population: Pop_residual_from_corrected_layer
 - ii. Land cover merged: raster_land_cover_merged_Landcover_merge_1 km
 - iii. Scenario table: Supplementary Table_t_scenario_walk_dry
 - iv. Select existing health facilities layer (vector): Potential_ASC_VF
 - v. ID field: pointid
 - vi. Facility name field: cat
 - vii. Capacity: big_capaci (10000000 used to effectively ignore maximum population capacity)
 - viii. Select zones layer (vector): Limite_Mali_32629
 1. Select zones unique ID (integer): objectid
 2. Select zone name (text): Nom_Region
- b. We used the following analysis settings:
 - i. Type of analysis: anisotropic
 - ii. Direction of travel: towards facilities
 - iii. Facilities processing order according to: A field in the facility layer (big_capaci)
 - iv. Processing order: Descending
 - v. Maximum travel time (minutes): 30
 - vi. Options
 1. Compute population catchment area layer: Yes
 2. Remove the covered population at each iteration: Yes
 3. Compute a layer of population cells on barriers: Yes
 4. Generate zonal statistics: Yes (adm 0)
 5. Run the analysis without considering capacities: No
 6. Add column with original population sum under each facility’s travel time: Yes
 7. Optimize dynamically computation according to the scenario: Yes
 8. Add short tag: GC_30 min_walk_step1

We used a spatial join to join the population within each 30-minute catchment from the output “Dummy_GC_30 min_walk_step1” to the vector point file for the hypothetical ASC network “Potential_ASC_VF” as variable “PopAire” and saved the resulting file as “Potential_ASC_VF2_PopAire” to be used in the geographic coverage analysis in Step 2 below.

Step 2. Geographic coverage analysis of the estimated population beyond 5 km of a CSCoM or CSRef using the hypothetical ASC network deployed to prioritize the estimated population.

Overview of the step

Following the “dummy” geographic analysis in Step 1, we conducted the “real” geographic coverage analysis of the estimated population beyond 5km of a CSCom or CSRef using the hypothetical ASC network deployed to prioritize the estimated population. The outputs from this step helped answer research question 1.

Data preparation

Completed above in Step 1.

Analysis

We repeated the geographic coverage analysis from step 1 using the maximum capacity of each potential ASC site (variable “CAP”), removing the population at each iteration, and using the estimated population within the catchment of the potential ASC site (variable “PopAire”) for the processing order.

- c. We used the following data inputs:
 - i. Population: Pop_residual_from_corrected_layer
 - ii. Land cover merged: raster_land_cover_merged_Landcover_merge_1 km
 - iii. Scenario table: Supplementary Table_t_scenario_walk_dry
 - iv. Select existing health facilities layer (vector): Potential_ASC_VF2_PopAire
 - v. ID field: pointid
 - vi. Facility name field: cat
 - vii. Capacity: CAP
 - viii. Select zones layer (vector): Limite_Mali_32629
 - 1. Select zones unique ID (integer): objectid
 - 2. Select zone name (text): Nom_Region
- d. We used the following analysis settings:
 - i. Type of analysis: anisotropic
 - ii. Direction of travel: towards facilities
 - iii. Facilities processing order according to: A field in the facility layer (PopAire)
 - iv. Processing order: Descending
 - v. Maximum travel time (minutes): 30
 - vi. Options
 - 1. Compute population catchment area layer: Yes
 - 2. Remove the covered population at each iteration: Yes
 - 3. Compute a layer of population cells on barriers: Yes
 - 4. Generate zonal statistics: Yes (adm 0)
 - 5. Run the analysis without considering capacities: No
 - 6. Add column with original population sum under each facility’s travel time: Yes
 - 7. Optimize dynamically computation according to the scenario: Yes
 - 8. Add short tag: GC_30 min_walk_step2

Step 3. Geographic coverage analysis of the estimated U5 deaths beyond 5 km of a CSCom or CSRef using the hypothetical ASC network deployed to prioritize the estimated U5 deaths.

Overview of the step

The geographic coverage analysis in Step 3 helped answer research question 2 in terms of geographic coverage of the estimated U5 deaths by the hypothetical ASC network prioritizing estimated U5 deaths. It also provided the estimated U5 deaths for each ASC site catchment area (the area within a 30-minute walk from the ASC in dry conditions), variable “U5dAire”, providing the processing to be used in Step 6 (for research question 1) and Step 11 (for research question 3) for geographic coverage of the estimated population using the hypothetical ASC network prioritizing U5 deaths. Details are provided below.

Data preparation

See Methods section “Candidate ASC sites for optimized ASC networks” for details on preparation of the hypothetical ASC network.

See Methods section “Data preparation of the raster layer for the estimated U5 deaths beyond 5 km from a CSRef or CSCoM in 2020” for details on preparation of the raster layer for the estimated U5 deaths beyond 5 km from a CSRef or CSCoM in 2020.

Analysis

We conducted an analysis of the geographic coverage of the estimated U5 deaths beyond 5 km from a CSRef or CSCoM by the hypothetical network of ASC (n=12050 ASC sites with 15843 ASC) deployed to prioritize the estimated U5 deaths at 1 km x 1 km resolution for the walking in dry conditions travel scenario. We set the maximum travel time to 30 minutes. We set the maximum population capacity for ASCs as 10000000 to effectively ignore capacity. We used a descending processing order (highest to lowest) based on the estimated population beyond 5 km from a CSRef or CSCoM in 2020 within each 30-minute catchment area. This prioritized the deployment of the hypothetical ASC network according to the size (highest to lowest) of the estimated number of under-five deaths in areas beyond 5 km from a CSRef or CSCoM within each 30-minute catchment.

- a. We used the following data inputs:
 - i. Population: Pop_residual_from_corrected_layer
 - ii. Land cover merged: raster_land_cover_merged_Landcover_merge_1 km
 - iii. Scenario table: Supplementary Table_t_scenario_walk_dry
 - iv. Select existing health facilities layer (vector): Potential_ASC_VF2
 - v. ID field: pointid
 - vi. Facility name field: cat
 - vii. Capacity: big_capaci (10000000 used to effectively ignore maximum population capacity)
 - viii. Select zones layer (vector): Limite_Mali_32629
 1. Select zones unique ID (integer): objectid
 2. Select zone name (text): Nom_Region
- b. We used the following analysis settings:
 - i. Type of analysis: anisotropic
 - ii. Direction of travel: towards facilities
 - iii. Facilities processing order according to: The population (U5 deaths) living within a given travel time from the facilities
 - iv. Processing order: Descending
 - v. Maximum travel time (minutes): 30
 - vi. Options
 1. Compute population catchment area layer: Yes
 2. Remove the covered population at each iteration: Yes
 3. Compute a layer of population cells on barriers: Yes
 4. Generate zonal statistics: Yes (adm 0)
 5. Run the analysis without considering capacities: No
 6. Add column with original population sum under each facility’s travel time: Yes
 7. Optimize dynamically computation according to the scenario: Yes
 8. Add short tag: GC_30 min_walk_step3

We used a spatial join to join the U5 deaths within each 30-minute catchment from the output “Dummy_GC_30 min_walk_step3” to the vector point file for the hypothetical ASC network “Potential_ASC_VF” as variable “U5dAire” and saved the resulting file as “Potential_ASC_VF2_U5dAire” to be used in the geographic coverage analysis in Step 6 and Step 11 below.

Step 4. “Dummy” geographic coverage analysis of the estimated *Pf* malaria cases beyond 5 km of a CSCoM or CSRef using the hypothetical ASC network deployed to prioritize the estimated *Pf* malaria cases.

Overview of the step

The “dummy” geographic coverage analysis in Step 4 helped to derive the estimated *Pf* malaria cases for each ASC site catchment area (the area within a 30-minute walk from the ASC in dry conditions), variable “CasesAire”, which was used for the processing order in Step 5 (answers research question 3), Step 7 (answers research question 1) and Step 9 (answers research question 2) for the hypothetical ASC network deployed to prioritize the estimated *Pf* malaria cases.

Data preparation

See Methods section “Candidate ASC sites for optimized ASC networks” for details on preparation of the hypothetical ASC network.

See Methods section “Data preparation of the raster layer for the estimated *Pf* malaria cases beyond 5 km from a CSRef or CSCoM in 2020” for details on preparation of the raster layer for the estimated *Pf* malaria cases beyond 5 km from a CSRef or CSCoM in 2020.

Analysis

We conducted a “dummy” geographic coverage analysis of the estimated *Pf* malaria cases in areas beyond 5 km from the CSRef or CSCoM in 2020 by the hypothetical network of ASC (n=12050 ASC sites with 15843 ASC) deployed to prioritize the estimated *Pf* malaria cases at 1 km x 1 km resolution for the walking in dry conditions travel scenario. We set the maximum travel time to 30 minutes. We set the maximum population capacity for ASCs as 10000000 to effectively ignore capacity. We used a descending processing order (highest to lowest) based on the estimated *Pf* malaria cases beyond 5 km from a CSRef or CSCoM in 2020 within each 30-minute catchment area. This prioritized the deployment of the hypothetical ASC network according to the size (highest to lowest) of the estimated *Pf* malaria cases in areas beyond 5 km from a CSRef or CSCoM within each 30-minute catchment.

- a. We used the following data inputs:
 - i. Population: Number_Malaria_cases_residual_final
 - ii. Land cover merged: raster_land_cover_merged_Landcover_merge_1 km
 - iii. Scenario table: Supplementary Table_t_scenario_walk_dry
 - iv. Select existing health facilities layer (vector): Potential_ASC_VF
 - v. ID field: pointid
 - vi. Facility name field: cat
 - vii. Capacity: big_capaci (10000000 used to effectively ignore maximum population capacity)
 - viii. Select zones layer (vector): Limite_Mali_32629
 1. Select zones unique ID (integer): objectid
 2. Select zone name (text): Nom_Region
- b. We used the following analysis settings:
 - i. Type of analysis: anisotropic
 - ii. Direction of travel: towards facilities
 - iii. Facilities processing order according to: A field in the facility layer (PopAire)
 - iv. Processing order: Descending
 - v. Maximum travel time (minutes): 30
 - vi. Options
 1. Compute population catchment area layer: Yes
 2. Remove the covered population at each iteration: Yes
 3. Compute a layer of population cells on barriers: Yes
 4. Generate zonal statistics: Yes (adm 0)
 5. Run the analysis without considering capacities: No
 6. Add column with original population sum under each facility’s travel time: Yes
 7. Optimize dynamically computation according to the scenario: Yes
 8. Add short tag: GC_30 min_walk_step4

We used a spatial join to join the *Pf* malaria cases within each 30-minute catchment from the output “Dummy_GC_30 min_walk_step4” to the vector point file for the hypothetical ASC network “Potential_ASC_VF” as variable “CasesAire” and saved the resulting file as “Potential_ASC_VF2_CasesAire” to be used in the geographic coverage analysis in Step 5, Step 7, and Step 9 below.

Step 5. Geographic coverage analysis of the estimated *Pf* malaria cases beyond 5 km of a CCom or CSRef using the hypothetical ASC network deployed to prioritize the estimated *Pf* malaria cases.

Overview of the step

Following the “dummy” geographic analysis in Step 4, we conducted the “real” geographic coverage analysis of the estimated *Pf* malaria cases beyond 5km of a CCom or CSRef using the hypothetical ASC network deployed to prioritize the estimated *Pf* malaria cases. The outputs from this step helped answer research question 3.

Data preparation

Completed above in Step 4.

Analysis

We repeated the geographic coverage analysis from step 4 using the maximum capacity of each potential ASC site (variable “CAP”), removing the population at each iteration, and using the estimated *Pf* malaria cases within the catchment of the potential ASC site (variable “CasesAire”) for the processing order.

- a. We used the following data inputs:
 - i. Population: Number_Malaria_cases_residual_final
 - ii. Land cover merged: raster_land_cover_merged_Landcover_merge_1 km
 - iii. Scenario table: Supplementary Table_t_scenario_walk_dry
 - iv. Select existing health facilities layer (vector): Potential_ASC_VF2_CasesAire
 - v. ID field: pointid
 - vi. Facility name field: cat
 - vii. Capacity: CAP
 - viii. Select zones layer (vector): Limite_Mali_32629
 1. Select zones unique ID (integer): objectid
 2. Select zone name (text): Nom_Region
- b. We used the following analysis settings:
 - i. Type of analysis: anisotropic
 - ii. Direction of travel: towards facilities
 - iii. Facilities processing order according to: A field in the facility layer (CasesAire)
 - iv. Processing order: Descending
 - v. Maximum travel time (minutes): 30
 - vi. Options
 1. Compute population catchment area layer: Yes
 2. Remove the covered population at each iteration: Yes
 3. Compute a layer of population cells on barriers: Yes
 4. Generate zonal statistics: Yes (adm 0)
 5. Run the analysis without considering capacities: No
 6. Add column with original population sum under each facility’s travel time: Yes
 7. Optimize dynamically computation according to the scenario: Yes
 8. Add short tag: GC_30 min_walk_step5

Step 6. Geographic coverage analysis of the estimated population beyond 5 km of a CCom or CSRef using the hypothetical ASC network deployed to prioritize the estimated U5 deaths.

Overview of the step

We conducted a geographic coverage analysis of the estimated population beyond 5km of a CSCCom or CSRef using the hypothetical ASC network deployed to prioritize the estimated U5 deaths. The outputs from this step helped answer research question 1.

Data preparation

Completed above in Step 3.

Analysis

We conducted the geographic coverage analysis using the maximum capacity of each potential ASC site (variable “CAP”), removing the population at each iteration, and using the estimated U5 deaths within the catchment of the potential ASC site (variable “U5dAire”) for the processing order.

- a. We used the following data inputs:
 - i. Population: Pop_residual_from_corrected_layer
 - ii. Land cover merged: raster_land_cover_merged_Landcover_merge_1 km
 - iii. Scenario table: Supplementary Table_t_scenario_walk_dry
 - iv. Select existing health facilities layer (vector): Potential_ASC_VF2_U5dAire
 - v. ID field: pointid
 - vi. Facility name field: cat
 - vii. Capacity: CAP
 - viii. Select zones layer (vector): Limite_Mali_32629
 1. Select zones unique ID (integer): objectid
 2. Select zone name (text): Nom_Region
- b. We used the following analysis settings:
 - i. Type of analysis: anisotropic
 - ii. Direction of travel: towards facilities
 - iii. Facilities processing order according to: A field in the facility layer (U5dAire)
 - iv. Processing order: Descending
 - v. Maximum travel time (minutes): 30
 - vi. Options
 1. Compute population catchment area layer: Yes
 2. Remove the covered population at each iteration: Yes
 3. Compute a layer of population cells on barriers: Yes
 4. Generate zonal statistics: Yes (adm 0)
 5. Run the analysis without considering capacities: No
 6. Add column with original population sum under each facility’s travel time: Yes
 7. Optimize dynamically computation according to the scenario: Yes
 8. Add short tag: GC_30 min_walk_step6

Step 7. Geographic coverage analysis of the estimated population beyond 5 km of a CSCCom or CSRef using the hypothetical ASC network deployed to prioritize the estimated *Pf* malaria cases.

Overview of the step

We conducted a geographic coverage analysis of the estimated population beyond 5km of a CSCCom or CSRef using the hypothetical ASC network deployed to prioritize the estimated *Pf* malaria cases. The outputs from this step helped answer research question 1.

Data preparation

Completed above in Step 5.

Analysis

We conducted the geographic coverage analysis using the maximum capacity of each potential ASC site (variable “CAP”), removing the population at each iteration, and using the estimated *Pf* malaria cases within the catchment of the potential ASC site (variable “CasesAire”) for the processing order.

- a. We used the following data inputs:
 - i. Population: Pop_residual_from_corrected_layer
 - ii. Land cover merged: raster_land_cover_merged_Landcover_merge_1 km
 - iii. Scenario table: Supplementary Table_t_scenario_walk_dry
 - iv. Select existing health facilities layer (vector): Potential_ASC_VF2_CasesAire
 - v. ID field: pointid
 - vi. Facility name field: cat
 - vii. Capacity: CAP
 - viii. Select zones layer (vector): Limite_Mali_32629
 1. Select zones unique ID (integer): objectid
 2. Select zone name (text): Nom_Region
- b. We used the following analysis settings:
 - i. Type of analysis: anisotropic
 - ii. Direction of travel: towards facilities
 - iii. Facilities processing order according to: A field in the facility layer (CasesAire)
 - iv. Processing order: Descending
 - v. Maximum travel time (minutes): 30
 - vi. Options
 1. Compute population catchment area layer: Yes
 2. Remove the covered population at each iteration: Yes
 3. Compute a layer of population cells on barriers: Yes
 4. Generate zonal statistics: Yes (adm 0)
 5. Run the analysis without considering capacities: No
 6. Add column with original population sum under each facility’s travel time: Yes
 7. Optimize dynamically computation according to the scenario: Yes
 8. Add short tag: GC_30 min_walk_step7

Step 8. Geographic coverage analysis of the estimated U5 deaths beyond 5 km of a CSCom or CSRef using the hypothetical ASC network deployed to prioritize the estimated population.

Overview of the step

We conducted a geographic coverage analysis of the estimated U5 deaths beyond 5km of a CSCom or CSRef using the hypothetical ASC network deployed to prioritize the estimated population. The outputs from this step helped answer research question 2.

Data preparation

Completed above in Step 2.

Analysis

We conducted the geographic coverage analysis using the maximum capacity of each potential ASC site (variable “CAP”), removing the population at each iteration, and using the estimated population within the catchment of the potential ASC site (variable “PopAire”) for the processing order.

- a. We used the following data inputs:
 - i. Population: Number_of_residual_death_U5
 - ii. Land cover merged: raster_land_cover_merged_Landcover_merge_1 km
 - iii. Scenario table: Supplementary Table_t_scenario_walk_dry
 - iv. Select existing health facilities layer (vector): Potential_ASC_VF2_PopAire

- v. ID field: pointid
- vi. Facility name field: cat
- vii. Capacity: CAP
- viii. Select zones layer (vector): Limite_Mali_32629
 - 1. Select zones unique ID (integer): objectid
 - 2. Select zone name (text): Nom_Region
- b. We used the following analysis settings:
 - i. Type of analysis: anisotropic
 - ii. Direction of travel: towards facilities
 - iii. Facilities processing order according to: A field in the facility layer (PopAire)
 - iv. Processing order: Descending
 - v. Maximum travel time (minutes): 30
 - vi. Options
 - 1. Compute population catchment area layer: Yes
 - 2. Remove the covered population at each iteration: Yes
 - 3. Compute a layer of population cells on barriers: Yes
 - 4. Generate zonal statistics: Yes (adm 0)
 - 5. Run the analysis without considering capacities: No
 - 6. Add column with original population sum under each facility's travel time: Yes
 - 7. Optimize dynamically computation according to the scenario: Yes
 - 8. Add short tag: GC_30 min_walk_step8

Step 9. Geographic coverage analysis of the estimated U5 deaths beyond 5 km of a CSCom or CSRef using the hypothetical ASC network deployed to prioritize the estimated *Pf* malaria cases.

Overview of the step

We conducted a geographic coverage analysis of the estimated U5 deaths beyond 5km of a CSCom or CSRef using the hypothetical ASC network deployed to prioritize the estimated *Pf* malaria cases. The outputs from this step helped answer research question 2.

Data preparation

Completed above in Step 4.

Analysis

We conducted the geographic coverage analysis using the maximum capacity of each potential ASC site (variable “CAP”), removing the population at each iteration, and using the estimated *Pf* malaria cases within the catchment of the potential ASC site (variable “CasesAire”) for the processing order.

- a. We used the following data inputs:
 - i. Population: Number_of_residual_death_U5
 - ii. Land cover merged: raster_land_cover_merged_Landcover_merge_1 km
 - iii. Scenario table: Supplementary Table_t_scenario_walk_dry
 - iv. Select existing health facilities layer (vector): Potential_ASC_VF2_CasesAire
 - v. ID field: pointid
 - vi. Facility name field: cat
 - vii. Capacity: CAP
 - viii. Select zones layer (vector): Limite_Mali_32629
 - 1. Select zones unique ID (integer): objectid
 - 2. Select zone name (text): Nom_Region
- b. We used the following analysis settings:
 - i. Type of analysis: anisotropic
 - ii. Direction of travel: towards facilities

- iii. Facilities processing order according to: A field in the facility layer (CasesAire)
- iv. Processing order: Descending
- v. Maximum travel time (minutes): 30
- vi. Options
 - 1. Compute population catchment area layer: Yes
 - 2. Remove the covered population at each iteration: Yes
 - 3. Compute a layer of population cells on barriers: Yes
 - 4. Generate zonal statistics: Yes (adm 0)
 - 5. Run the analysis without considering capacities: No
 - 6. Add column with original population sum under each facility's travel time: Yes
 - 7. Optimize dynamically computation according to the scenario: Yes
 - 8. Add short tag: GC_30 min_walk_step9

Step 10. Geographic coverage analysis of the estimated *Pf* malaria cases beyond 5 km of a CSCom or CSRef using the hypothetical ASC network deployed to prioritize the estimated population.

Overview of the step

We conducted a geographic coverage analysis of the estimated *Pf* malaria cases beyond 5km of a CSCom or CSRef using the hypothetical ASC network deployed to prioritize the estimated population. The outputs from this step helped answer research question 3.

Data preparation

Completed above in Step 2.

Analysis

We conducted the geographic coverage analysis using the maximum capacity of each potential ASC site (variable “CAP”), removing the population at each iteration, and using the estimated population within the catchment of the potential ASC site (variable “PopAire”) for the processing order.

- a. We used the following data inputs:
 - i. Population: Number_Malaria_cases_residual_final
 - ii. Land cover merged: raster_land_cover_merged_Landcover_merge_1 km
 - iii. Scenario table: Supplementary Table_t_scenario_walk_dry
 - iv. Select existing health facilities layer (vector): Potential_ASC_VF2_PopAire
 - v. ID field: pointid
 - vi. Facility name field: cat
 - vii. Capacity: CAP
 - viii. Select zones layer (vector): Limite_Mali_32629
 - 1. Select zones unique ID (integer): objectid
 - 2. Select zone name (text): Nom_Region
- b. We used the following analysis settings:
 - i. Type of analysis: anisotropic
 - ii. Direction of travel: towards facilities
 - iii. Facilities processing order according to: A field in the facility layer (PopAire)
 - iv. Processing order: Descending
 - v. Maximum travel time (minutes): 30
 - vi. Options
 - 1. Compute population catchment area layer: Yes
 - 2. Remove the covered population at each iteration: Yes
 - 3. Compute a layer of population cells on barriers: Yes
 - 4. Generate zonal statistics: Yes (adm 0)
 - 5. Run the analysis without considering capacities: No

6. Add column with original population sum under each facility's travel time: Yes
7. Optimize dynamically computation according to the scenario: Yes
8. Add short tag: GC_30 min_walk_step10

Step 11. Geographic coverage analysis of the estimated *Pf* malaria cases beyond 5 km of a CCom or CSRef using the hypothetical ASC network deployed to prioritize the estimated U5 deaths.

Overview of the step

We conducted a geographic coverage analysis of the estimated *Pf* malaria cases beyond 5km of a CCom or CSRef using the hypothetical ASC network deployed to prioritize the estimated U5 deaths. The outputs from this step helped answer research question 3.

Data preparation

Completed above in Step 3.

Analysis

We conducted the geographic coverage analysis using the maximum capacity of each potential ASC site (variable "CAP"), removing the population at each iteration, and using the estimated population within the catchment of the potential ASC site (variable "U5dAire") for the processing order.

- a. We used the following data inputs:
 - i. Population: Number_Malaria_cases_residual_final
 - ii. Land cover merged: raster_land_cover_merged_Landcover_merge_1 km
 - iii. Scenario table: Supplementary Table_t_scenario_walk_dry
 - iv. Select existing health facilities layer (vector): Potential_ASC_VF2_U5dAire
 - v. ID field: pointid
 - vi. Facility name field: cat
 - vii. Capacity: CAP
 - viii. Select zones layer (vector): Limite_Mali_32629
 1. Select zones unique ID (integer): objectid
 2. Select zone name (text): Nom_Region
- b. We used the following analysis settings:
 - i. Type of analysis: anisotropic
 - ii. Direction of travel: towards facilities
 - iii. Facilities processing order according to: A field in the facility layer (U5dAire)
 - iv. Processing order: Descending
 - v. Maximum travel time (minutes): 30
 - vi. Options
 1. Compute population catchment area layer: Yes
 2. Remove the covered population at each iteration: Yes
 3. Compute a layer of population cells on barriers: Yes
 4. Generate zonal statistics: Yes (adm 0)
 5. Run the analysis without considering capacities: No
 6. Add column with original population sum under each facility's travel time: Yes
 7. Optimize dynamically computation according to the scenario: Yes
 8. Add short tag: GC_30 min_walk_step11

References

1. NASA JPL. 2013. NASA Shuttle Radar Topography Mission Global 1 arc second v003 [database]. NASA EOSDIS Land Processes DAAC. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5067/MEaSURES/SRTM/SRTMGL1.003> [Accessed 7 Feb 2021].
2. WorldPop and Statistics Sierra Leone. 2021. Census disaggregated gridded population estimates for Sierra Leone (2015), version 2.0 [database]. University of Southampton. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5258/SOTON/WP00714> [Accessed 12 Jul 2021].
3. Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation (IHME). 2019. Low- and Middle-Income Country Neonatal, Infant, and Under-5 Mortality Geospatial Estimates 2000-2017 [database]. Seattle, United States: Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation. Available: <http://ghdx.healthdata.org/lbd-data> [Accessed 3 Mar 2020].
4. Weiss DJ, Lucas TCD, Nguyen M, et al. Mapping the global prevalence, incidence, and mortality of *Plasmodium falciparum*, 2000-2017: a spatial and temporal modelling study. *Lancet* 2019;394(10195):322–.doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(19)31097-9
5. Institut Géographique du Mali. Routes_du_pays_32629 [database]. Institut Géographique du Mali. [Obtained from Institut Géographique du Mali on 12 Jan 2022].
6. Buchhorn M, Smets B, Bertels L, De Roo B, Lesiv M, Tsendbazar N-E, et al. Copernicus Global Land Service: Land Cover 100M:collection 3:epoch 2015:Globe 2020 [database]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3939038> [Accessed 27 Mar 2018].
7. Ray N, Ebener S. AccessMod 3.0: computing geographic coverage and accessibility to health care services using anisotropic movement of patients. *Int J Health Geogr* 2008;7:63.doi:10.1186/1476-072X-7-63
8. Ministère de la Santé et du Développement Social. CARTOGRAPHIE_ASC_MARS_2021_DGSHP_31.03.2021_VF2 [database]. Bamako: Ministère de la Santé et du Développement Social; 2021. Unpublished database.
9. HeRAMS Mali. Health Resources and Services Availability Monitoring System, Mali. Available from <https://herams.org>. Accessed 7 17 Dec 2021.
10. Institut National de la Statistique (INSTAT) du Mali. INSTAT Population 2020 Commune [database]. Institut National de la Statistique (INSTAT) du Mali. Available in Public Data Repository at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6551988>
11. Institut Géographique du Mali. Limite_Mali_32629 [database]. Institut Géographique du Mali. [Obtained from Institut Géographique du Mali on 17 Dec 2021]. Available in Public Data Repository at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6551988>
12. Institut Géographique du Mali. Limite_Region_32629 [database]. Institut Géographique du Mali. [Obtained from Institut Géographique du Mali on 17 Dec 2021]. Available in Public Data Repository at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6551988>
13. Institut Géographique du Mali. Lim_Com [database]. Institut Géographique du Mali. [Obtained from Institut Géographique du Mali on 17 Dec 2021]. Available in Public Data Repository at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6551988>
14. QGIS.org. QGIS Geographic Information System. 3.18.2-Zürich ed: Open Source Geospatial Foundation; 2021.

15. Ministère de la Santé et du Développement Social et Ministère de la Promotion de la Femme, de l'Enfant et de la Famille. Programme de development socio-sanitaire 2020-2023 (PRODESS IV). Bamako: Ministère de la Santé et du Développement Social et Ministère de la Promotion de la Femme, de l'Enfant et de la Famille, La République du Mali; 2021.
16. Ministère de la Santé et de l'Hygiene Publique. Plan Stratégique National des Soins Essentiels dans la Communauté 2016-2020. Bamako: Ministère de la Santé et de l'Hygiene Publique; 2015.
17. Oliphant NP, Ray N, Bensaid K, et al. Optimising geographical accessibility to primary health care: a geospatial analysis of community health posts and community health workers in Niger. *BMJ Global Health* 2021;6:e005238. doi:10.1136/bmjgh-2021-005238
18. Huerta Munoz U, Källestål C. Geographical accessibility and spatial coverage modeling of the primary health care network in the Western Province of Rwanda. *Int J Health Geogr* 2012;11:40.doi:10.1186/1476-072X-11-40
19. Breiman, L. Random forests. *Mach. Learn* 2001;45:5–32.doi:10.1023/A:1010933404324
20. Stevens FR, Gaughan AE, Linard C et al. Disaggregating Census Data for Population Mapping Using Random Forests with Remotely-Sensed and Ancillary Data. *PLoS ONE* 2015;10:e0107042.doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0107042
21. Dooley, C. A., Boo, G., Leasure, D.R. and Tatem, A.J. 2020. Gridded maps of building patterns throughout sub-Saharan Africa, version 1.1. WorldPop, University of Southampton. Source of building footprints: Ecopia Vector Maps Powered by Maxar Satellite Imagery (C) 2020. doi:10.5258/SOTON/WP00677
22. WorldPop (www.worldpop.org - School of Geography and Environmental Science, University of Southampton). 2017. Mali 1km births. Version 2.0 2015 estimates of numbers of live births per grid square, with national totals adjusted to match UN national estimates on numbers of live births (<http://esa.un.org/wpp/>). DOI: 10.5258/SOTON/WP00387 [Accessed 17 Dec 2021].
23. WorldPop (www.worldpop.org - School of Geography and Environmental Science, University of Southampton; Department of Geography and Geosciences, University of Louisville; Departement de Géographie, Université de Namur) and Center for International Earth Science Information Network (CIESIN), Columbia University (2018). Global High Resolution Population Denominators Project - Funded by The Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation (OPP1134076). <https://dx.doi.org/10.5258/SOTON/WP00670>